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Research and Innovation Action

Topic: EeB-07-2015 New tools and methodologies to reduce the gap between predicted and actual energy performances at the level of buildings and blocks of buildings

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D7.2 Market Communication Strategy

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Executive Summary

This document sets out the HIT2GAP Marketing and Communications strategy and the roles and responsibilities of all 22 Project Partners in delivering the project aims how success will be measured.

The marketing and communication strategy links back to the original project work plan which outlines the intentions with regard to communication, dissemination and exploitation and the delivery role of the project partners. The overall aim is to align the project within a strategic innovation context and to make the project foreground scalable, replicable and high impact. It should be read in conjunction with Appendices 1: National Stakeholder Forum, 2: Initial Exploitation and Business Plan, and 3: Guidance for journal and conference paper submission and with reference to section 2 (Impact) of the original HIT2GAP project submission.

The engagement of national and overall project Stakeholder Forums is seen as crucial to the project's success. This will be constructed at a national level by individual partners with recommendations sought for participation at a project level. Throughout the duration of the project, this body is informed, engaged, and invited to participate in project events, project results, and progress with the objective of them becoming advocates of project exploitable results and in time the early and first adopters of the HIT2GAP approach, solution and services.

The Group will cover a broad spectrum within the 'dissemination space' and include the full range of stakeholders types / actors (building owners, energy managers, facility management companies, technology providers, building and sustainability consultants).

Beyond this the project team will work beyond the consortium boundaries to include other sectors and other markets. Sector awareness, IPR positioning and deliberate technology and patent scouting will ensure that the project can position its foreground correctly and in a strong way. This is conducted by a dedicated exploitation partner (R2M) and leads into the management of exploitable results.

The overall purpose of Task 7.2 is to set up a platform that all partners should use for all aspects of project communication, from internal, cross partner communication to academic outputs to public awareness raising to promote buy-in to the project. This will include the development of a project 'brand' with cross-sectoral appeal in addition to the HIT2GAP logo this includes a project website, flyer, newsletter and presentation materials.

The key aspects are as follows:

- To facilitate identification of commercial targets for the project.
- To allow partners to communicate internally and externally through simple explanations of the research goals and findings, which can be understood by non-specialists.
- To support partners in presentation of the findings and developments of the project at relevant conferences in both academic, industrial and public sector arenas.

A public web portal has been developed in accordance to the internal guidelines of the project partners to disseminate the goals and findings of the research. In the first instance this is a

dedicated HIT2GAP project website, however as the project develops the focus will shift to media that can ensure a lasting legacy for the project beyond the life of the H2020 project funding.

Whenever possible, HIT2GAP will also cooperate with other R&D projects (especially those funded under the same H2020 call) on dissemination and awareness activities (exhibitions, stakeholder workshops, etc.) to ensure harmonised communications and greater impacts.

This task will plan and synchronize communication and dissemination activities so that they are systematic, managed and part of a project-level strategy. They will also reinforce and be linked to exploitation to build awareness (branding) and create demand. Assessment indicators will be assigned for the various communication and dissemination channels and responsibilities for those assessments will be assigned.

1 Objectives of the project

The HIT2GAP Project objectives are outlined below:

“The ‘performance gap’ between the design and operation of a building’s energy performance is well documented and verified by measurement campaigns. It is well documented that common errors across the four phases of construction can lead to a performance gap that ranges between 150-250% of the original design specification. Systematically addressing these errors and thus reducing the gap between design and performance is the main objective of the HIT2GAP project“.

HIT2GAP will link enabling technologies and approaches used in the operation phase of construction to improve the comparative predictions of the models and simulations that drive design, construction and the actual performance of new and retrofit buildings. To do this, the project will undertake the challenge of defining and enabling new solutions and products for building energy management which out-perform proprietary systems, with a view to identifying opportunities to improve existing approaches and enabling new innovations to come into the market. As such, **HIT2GAP aims to link large system providers and small but highly innovative start-up companies by providing a platform that can integrate third-party systems and applications.**

To address the climatic variance across the EU, HIT2GAP will use a ‘plug and play’ approach for integrating tools and applications, with continuous tool evaluation procedures to provide adapted solutions for each building. In selecting and developing its technologies, HIT2GAP specifically addresses existing Building Management System (BMS) limitations, which include challenges around the following:

1. Automatic analysis of data to identify significant deviations from the norm and to generate alarms to help improve understanding, assessment and optimisation of energy performance.
2. Provision of an energy reference model for the monitored building against which baseline evaluation of building energy performance can be compared.
3. Linking of energy consumption with occupant activities and behaviour.
4. Integration of different data sources (wireless sensors, social data, web sensors, etc.) and solutions/modules (analysis, diagnosis, prediction, etc.) from different providers on several levels. This is problematic due to non-standardisation of a unified BMS modular architecture and BMS development and implementation rules and protocols.
5. Intuitive adaptation of BMS Human Computer Interaction (HCI) tools to specific contexts and needs.

By embracing an open, plug and play, application-based approach, HIT2GAP will provide a platform that will support a new generation of BMS that can evolve and remain up-to-date as new technologies emerge.

2 Communication objectives, principles and key messages

Building performance and wider energy-related research projects often fail to reach the audiences that could deliver the opportunities identified. As a result recommendations remain nothing more than words on paper and new tools are developed but never see the light of day, remaining buried on unpublicised websites and other inaccessible repositories, resulting in the same ideas being re-invented years later.

HIT2GAP addresses a well-recognised issue that has been explored at a variety of levels in past projects. However, the timing is now right and the mechanisms exist to both develop and implement useful outcomes across the spectrum – from research and academia, through design, to construction and operation of buildings. It is therefore more important than ever before that the outcomes of this project are effectively communicated in order to both disseminate the project recommendations and products timeously to those who would benefit and to effect real change in construction design and operation practice. Key to this will be a mix of well-targeted, traditional and innovative communication platforms.

The approach to the overall communications strategy is to:

- help achieve overall project related objectives through effective internal knowledge sharing across the project partners;
- ensure effective engagement with key external stakeholders;
- demonstrate the success and effectiveness of the HIT2GAP project; and
- create a useful and accessible legacy for the project.

In order to effect the following:

- the creation and accessibility of better modelling and appraisal tools and Building Management systems; and
- change behaviour and perceptions across the industry where necessary and with building users more generally.

At a macro and global level, the approach and methodology proposed within HIT2GAP is as follows:

- to include all stakeholders involved in the process of energy management of a building from the concept phase until the maintenance and exploitation phases within the whole life of a building;
- to develop a framework and IT developments in parallel to enable partner co-operation and thus to ensure a robust approach;
- to run extensive and long duration (long enough to make a strong and powerful demonstration) pilot activities;

- to develop in parallel: an analysis of the associated business models to allow the definition of a new generation of services based on intelligent tools for buildings data treatment - this analysis will be conducted keeping a coherence of the business models developed with the regulation currently applicable in the European countries.

Summary

The general objective of all project communications is to ensure that any useful outcomes of the project are effectively deployed. This communications strategy is developed in line with EU guidelines, by BRE in co-operation with other partners. It demonstrates how the project's key messages and results will be disseminated and communicated across the project length. This includes elements such as the target groups, with tools and key actions.

The intention is to use a variety of instruments such as: websites; social media; audio visuals; press; TV and Radio; events and networking; publications and promotion materials with a view to leveraging the existing mechanisms and channels used by project partners' marketing departments. The objectives and principles underpinning this communication strategy are outlined below.

In the first instance, it is recommended that the outcomes of this work program should be disseminated and shared via the HIT2GAP website and through six monthly newsletters (to which all partners will be invited to contribute) across all teams taking part in this project. The format for the newsletters is outlined in the Deliverable 7.3 (Public Communication Materials). Secondly, as milestones are reached and the project develops, the extent of communication via the aforementioned routes and through project reports could be expanded more widely across the Horizon2020 network. At agreed points in time, outcomes will be reported in appropriate refereed journals, at relevant conferences, and through stakeholder workshops. On completion of the project outcomes will be disseminated via the traditional routes of trade and professional journals and through stakeholder workshops and seminars.

Stakeholder forums at a national and project level will provide a platform for testing and reality checking of outcomes. Associated workshops and seminars will provide not only opportunities for communication between stakeholders but may also flag issues in the form of case studies or live deployment opportunities to address a specific issue. Stakeholder forums will also facilitate communication beyond the immediate boundaries of the project will be effected by the HIT2GAP partners in conjunction with identified stakeholder groups and other interested parties, in order to test the commercial implications and feasibility of outcomes and with a view to identifying and addressing issues or concerns and to compare the project partners' perceptions with the reality faced by stakeholders day to day.

Highlights of Period 1 communication and dissemination activities include the following:

- the delivery of 5 local area workshops in partner countries that begin to build a brand image for the project and solicit stakeholder input;
- the formation of the HIT2GAP Stakeholder Forums;
- the development of baseline project communication materials (newsletter, brochure, presentation, press release, logo);

- the development of the project's online and social media footprint (webpage, Flipboard, LinkedIn, twitter, and potentially a Facebook page);
- the development of key messages and the visuals to support them;
- the development of communication and dissemination channels (partner networks, media contacts, EU channels).

3 HIT2GAP Audiences

Audience	Approach
Project Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Internally through contributions to the website, newsletter and externally to peers and influencers via conference and journal article opportunities, etc. To all via social media, web and Flipboard. ▪ Set up HIT2GAP as LinkedIn group.
	People who can influence uptake/ long term success
Professional Bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Engage with professional institutions through journal articles and workshops/ seminars/ conferences. ▪ Set up HIT2GAP LinkedIn group – publicise through Stakeholder Forums, Newsletter, Flyer, Web, etc.
Local Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Keep local government contacts such as sustainability, climate change, energy and building standards team aware of HIT2GAP and look for collaboration opportunities on other linked projects. ▪ Use Stakeholder Forum members to reinforce project messages and to engage directly with Local Government ▪ Use social media such as LinkedIn to set up HIT2GAP as something they might follow.
National Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Keep national government contacts such as sustainability, climate change, energy and building standards team aware of HIT2GAP and look for collaboration opportunities on other linked projects. ▪ Use Stakeholder Forum members to reinforce project messages and to engage directly with National Government. ▪ Use social media such as LinkedIn to set up HIT2GAP as something they might follow.
Research Funders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Bear in mind potential for future project phases and associate benefit in keeping the project progress in the line of sight of EC and other possible research funders.
BMS / Control system Manufacturers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Report on project in Trade Press and at trade Shows such as Interbuild and EcoBuild.
Software Developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Report on project in relevant publications – seek to engage on potential innovation projects.... New product opportunities, etc.
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Work with academic partners and others such as University Centres of Excellence. ▪ Report progress at academic conferences.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seek PhD / MSc opportunities.
	People and organisations directly impacted by the project
Construction Professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep aware through trade and professional press and at conferences such as CIBSE, ASHRAE, REHVA, etc.
Contractors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep aware through trade and professional press and at trade shows and through trade bodies, etc.
Building and Facilities Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep aware through trade and professional press and at trade shows and through trade bodies, etc.
BMS / Control system Manufacturers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep aware of developments and highlight opportunities likely to arise via trade press, CPD/ seminar presentations and trade shows, etc.
Software Developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep aware of developments and highlight opportunities likely to arise via relevant press, CPD/ seminar presentations, etc.
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep aware of developments and highlight opportunities likely to arise via seminar presentations and contributions to journals and conferences, etc.
	Organisations that can support the project
Professional Bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Work with to maximise spread of knowledge, seek formal engagement at events and through published articles.
Local Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Work with to maximise spread of knowledge and seek to clarify impact on local regulation and planning.
National Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Work with to maximise spread of knowledge and seek to clarify impact on national policy, regulation and planning.
Research Funders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bear in mind potential for future project phases and associate benefit in keeping the project progress in the line of sight of EC and other possible research funders. Look for funding opportunities to spread word and expand the project. Needs dialogue with known contacts in first instance.
BMS / Control system Manufacturers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can input to overcoming barriers and identifying solutions in addition to benefiting from sales opportunities.
Software Developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can input to overcoming barriers and identifying solutions in addition to benefiting from sales opportunities.
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can input to overcoming barriers and identifying solutions in addition to benefiting from research opportunities.

Construction Professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Support to further project aims, objectives and benefits.
Contractors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Support for implementation and tackling barriers. ▪ Identifying opportunities.
Building Managers; Facilities Managers; Building Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Support for implementation and training on benefits of implementation on building performance and users.
BMS / Control system Manufacturers; Software Developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Access to state of the current state of the art. ▪ Advice on practicality of emerging project outcomes. ▪ Provision of access to early adopters and test beds.
People or organisations indirectly impacted by the project	
Building Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Need to be apprised of impacts on building use. ▪ Feedback on practicality of proposed solutions.
Facilities Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Need to be apprised of impacts on building use. ▪ Feedback on practicality of proposed solutions.
Building Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Need to be apprised of impacts on building use. ▪ Feedback on practicality of proposed solutions.

4 Key Messages

<p>4.1 Project Objectives, Scope, Vision</p>	<p>The HIT2GAP project will deliver:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A generic information platform with protocols for communication with devices and user interfaces; 2. Building energy modelling, to establish energy consumption benchmarks; 3. A variety of tailored modules to inform users, energy managers and engineer. <p>The aims of the HIT2GAP project are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. to reduce the energy gap, focusing on the operation phase of buildings; 2. to propose a new paradigm for the development of energy management platforms in buildings, integrating existing expertise and resources; 3. to provide a smart platform which is marketable.
<p>4.2 Stakeholder Roles</p>	<p>Work Package leaders are as follows:</p> <p>WP1 – Requirements, framework and methodology to perform energy savings from data treatment (APINTECH)</p> <p>WP2 – Data acquisition solutions and software architecture (EURECAT)</p> <p>WP3 – Design, integration and test of data treatment bricks (FISE)</p> <p>WP4 – Design, integration and test of the software platform (NOBATEK)</p> <p>WP5 – Demonstration in pilot site (MOSTOSTAL)</p> <p>WP6 – Innovative services definition and market exploitation (R2M)</p> <p>WP7 – Dissemination and communication (BRE)</p> <p>WP8 – Organisation & Management strategy (NOBATEK)</p> <p>There are 22 partners in all; each will contribute to one or more Work Packages.</p>
<p>4.3 What to do, when, and why</p>	<p>See Section 6</p>
<p>4.4 Signposting and communication / discussion of ideas internally</p>	<p>The Flipboard will provide a facility for immediate communication of issues of interest raised by stakeholders and will communicate these to the wider group.</p> <p>These issues will be captured at stakeholder meetings and through feedback from HIT2GAP partners and building managers on issues that arise with the 4 Pilot projects.</p> <p>This will be reported more widely via the Newsletter.</p>

<p>4.5 Contributing Ideas – external organisations</p>	<p>The National Stakeholder Forums (see Appendix 1) will be drawn from a broad church of organisations in order to obtain regular input from a wide range of potential influencers, deliverers and users of buildings. These will be set up nationally within each Partner country (ideally around 25 stakeholders per country). In addition, each partner has been invited to nominate 2 stakeholders who will sit on an overall Project Stakeholder Forum to share ideas across national boundaries.</p> <p>Input from live projects will be contributed by participants in the 4 Pilot projects.</p> <p>This will be reported more widely via the Newsletter and Flyer, through which organisations beyond the project will be able to communicate their views.</p>
<p>4.6 How To...?</p>	<p>Stakeholder Forums will provide the initial opportunity for individuals and organisations to apprise themselves of the project developments and the potential to become ‘early adopters’.</p> <p>Communication to a wider audience will be effected through the Newsletter, Website and updated versions of the Flyer as the project evolves and potentially in the later stages via seminar and conference activity.</p>
<p>4.7 Business Readiness</p>	<p>Testing will be effected on the four Pilot projects in the first instance, issues identified and discussed with Stakeholder forums nationally and at a project level.</p> <p>Stakeholder forums will offer an opportunity to communicate outcomes and issues and to identify early adopters prior to any discussions around market roll out.</p>
<p>4.8 Measuring success</p>	<p>Measuring success, loops back to the use of the Stakeholder groups as project advocates and early adopters and replication beyond project partners. By creating demand during the project (stakeholder group + targeted dissemination) and by taking action during the project a future for HIT2GAP can be assured post project with the probability that this is high impact maximised. Increasing the innovation potential of stakeholders and end users via HIT2GAP uptake.</p> <p>HIT2GAP assembles a broad spectrum of end users, technology providers, consultants, and industrially active RTOs to both conduct the research and also to carry the project foreground to the market post project. Due to the diversity of the consortium partner stakeholder types, sectors of expertise and business geographic areas, the primary means of exploitation and business planning in HIT2GAP will be the integration of the HIT2GAP foreground into each partner’s current areas of business with the expectation that synergies and referrals will present themselves over the course of the collaboration.</p> <p>If it becomes clear that the next critical step for development and commercialisation requires continued joint development, a spinoff project may be considered.</p> <p>However, the preferred route is to consider joint exploitation opportunities and to follow a network of enterprises approach leveraging complementarities between clusters of partners and/or the synergies created by their geographic regions and/or networks.</p>

	The identification and management of exploitable results, market analysis and replication planning, and partner business planning are each dedicated tasks and/or activities in WP6 which will further develop and support joint exploitation development.
4.9 Thank You	Project completion party!

5 Communicators

In order for communications to be effective, the right people must be delivering the message. Who the right person is depends on the message and the audience. Consider who will be the key communicators throughout the project and what each will be responsible for. **This section should be read in conjunction with Appendix 2 – Initial Exploitation and Business Plan.**

Communicator	Objectives & Responsibilities
5.1 Sponsor - EC	<p>Funding</p> <p>Keeping the project on track – e.g. reaching of milestones, etc.</p> <p>Dissemination beyond the life of the project.</p>
5.2 Project Coordinator – NOBATEK	<p>Keeping the project partners on track – e.g. reaching of milestones, on time and making sure that reports submitted on time, etc.</p>
<p>5.3 Project Teams:</p> <p>5.4 NOBATEK – NBK</p> <p>5.5 EURECAT – EUR</p> <p>5.6 IK4-Tekniker (TEK)</p>	<p>All project teams have made a commitment which it is their duty to honour, on time and on budget. This is a publicly funded project, it is key to the future success of the project that all materials produced, while presenting market opportunities for the companies involved should be freely, openly and publicly available and advertised as such. All teams have a responsibility to communicate and promote the HIT2GAP story, however, specific responsibilities are listed below:</p> <p>As leaders of WPs 4 and 8, Nobatek should focus on aspects of communication and marketing relating to gathering market views on the platform design and practicalities of integration into existing processes and procedures.</p> <p>As leaders of WP 2, which is closely linked to WP 1, EURECAT should focus on aspects of communication and marketing relating to the development and testing of the HIT2GAP architecture, data treatment and management. In this they will be assisted by the leaders of Tasks 2.1, 2.2, 2.4, 2.5 and 2.6 – NBK, TEK, GAL, EGE and FISE.</p> <p>As leaders on Task 2.2/WP2 TEK should support EUR on communication related to WP2 and NBK on WP 1.</p>

Communicator		Objectives & Responsibilities
5.7	Fraunhofer Institute (FISE)	As leaders of WP 3 and Tasks 1.6, 2.6, FISE – will lead communication and marketing around the testing of the elementary modules arising from WP2 & WP 3 – Design, integration and testing of data treatment bricks and will support API and EUR on marketing of WP 1 and WP 2.
5.8	Building Research Establishment (BRE)	As leaders of WP 7 – Dissemination and Communication – BRE will lead on coordination and development of procedures for all dissemination activity. BRE will also contribute to dissemination in relation to WP6 Exploitation (with R2M) and WP5, Task 5.5 models for compliance testing.
5.9	Bouygues Energies & Services (BES)	As leaders of Task 5.3/WP 5, BES will support MOS by contributing to communication and marketing on the progress and outcomes of the Pilot Projects.
5.10	Giroa (GIR)	As key contributors to WP 5 and WP 6 GIR will contribute to communication and marketing in relation to project Exploitation and in particular on the progress and outcomes of the Pilot Projects.
5.11	Mostostal (MOS)	As leaders of WP 5 – Mostostal will lead on promotion, communication and marketing on the progress and outcomes of the Pilot Projects.
5.12	Cylon (CYL)	CYLON has major roles to play in promotion of the project on linked activities in WP 4, 5 and 6 – Design integration, Demonstration on pilot projects, and Market Exploitation. They will support WP leaders NBK, MOS and R2M in this work.
5.13	R2M	As leaders of WP 6 – Innovative services definition and Market Exploitation - R2M will work closely with the WP 7 leaders BRE on ensuring that opportunities to exploit the HIT2GAP outcomes are identified and taken up from the early stages and followed through via external opportunities.

Communicator	Objectives & Responsibilities
5.14 Abo Data (ABO)	<p>Abo Data's main contributions are in the areas of WP2, 4 and WP6 – Data acquisition and software architecture, Design integration and testing of the platform and Market Exploitation. They should support the WP leaders, EUR, NBK and R2M in communication related to these areas of work.</p>
5.15 Apintech (API)	<p>As leaders of WP1 and Technical Director of the project– Apintech will lead on awareness raising about the project and gathering information from those who deal with Building Energy Systems on a day to day basis to inform the project scope and tool requirements in order to maximise innovation.</p> <p>In particular on Task 1.1 – Methodology for adapting HIT2GAP to user requirements – they should use this opportunity to gather early information on user needs to relay to the rest of the team.</p>
5.16 CyRIC (CYR)	<p>CyRIC's main contributions are in the areas of WP2, 3 and WP 4 – Data acquisition and software architecture, Design integration, and testing of bricks and Design, integration and testing of the platform. They should support the WP leaders, EUR, FISE and NBK in communication related to these areas of work.</p>
5.17 Zutec (ZUT)	<p>ZUTEC's main contributions are in the areas of WP2, 3 and WP 4 – Data acquisition and software architecture, Design integration, and testing of bricks and Design, integration and testing of the platform. They should support the WP leaders, EUR, FISE and NBK in communication related to these areas of work.</p>
5.18 ENERIT (ENR)	<p>ENERIT's main contributions are in the areas of WP 1, 2, 4 and WP 5 – Framework, Data acquisition and software architecture, Design, integration and testing of the platform and Demonstration. They should support the WP</p>

Communicator	Objectives & Responsibilities
5.19 Evolution (EVL)	<p>leaders, API, EUR, NBK and MOS in communication related to these areas of work.</p> <p>Evolution's main contributions are in the areas of WP 3 - Design, integration and testing of data treatment bricks and WP 7 Dissemination and communication. They should support the WP leaders, FISE and BRE in communication activities.</p>
5.20 City of Warsaw (WRS)	<p>Warsaw's main contribution is in the areas of WP5 Pilot project demonstrations. They should contribute to communication and marketing in relation to the outcomes of the Pilot Projects and support the WP leaders, MOS in this area.</p>
5.21 Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour (LIUPPA)	<p>As leaders of Task 1.2 LIUPPA will support API in awareness raising about the project and gathering information from those who deal with Building Energy Systems on a day to day basis to inform the project scope and tool requirements in order to maximise innovation. LIUPPA also have significant roles on WP 2 and 4 - Data acquisition and software architecture and Design integration and testing of the platform. They should support the WP leaders, EUR, NBK and R2M in communication related to these areas of work.</p>
5.22 University of Girona (UDG)	<p>As Leaders of Task 1.3 WP 1, and Task 3.3 WP 3, UDG will support EUR in technical aspects of communicating framework development in WP 1 and FISE on testing of responses to the testing and validation of the platform in WP 3.</p>
5.23 University of Galway (GAL)	<p>As Leaders of Tasks 2.4 and 7.3 Galway will support EUR on promotion of exemplar applications to demonstrate the capabilities of HIT2GAP on WP 2 and will lead on the Scientific Diffusion elements of WP7 with BRE in support.</p>
5.24 University of Strathclyde (UoS)	<p>As leaders of Task 1.4 modelling and simulation and making a significant contribution to WP 2 and</p>

Communicator	Objectives & Responsibilities
5.25 Ege University - EGE	<p>WP 3 – Data acquisition and software architecture and Design integration, and testing of bricks plus WP 5 – Pilot Projects UoS will have responsibility for supporting the WP leaders, API, EUR, FISE and MOS in communication related to these areas of work.</p> <p>As leaders of Task 1.5 – User behaviour integration – and making a significant contribution to WP 2, and WP 3 – Data acquisition and software architecture and Design integration, and testing of bricks plus WP 5 – Pilot Projects EGE will have responsibility for supporting the WP leaders, API, EUR, FISE and MOS in communication related to these areas of work.</p>
5.26 Other Research Networks	Look for opportunities to promote through conferences and journals. See Appendix 3 for guidance on HIT2GAP procedures for preparation of conference and journal papers.
5.27 Nat/ Local Govt., etc.	<p>Link outcomes with existing and upcoming legislation.</p> <p>Make design and operation of buildings communities aware of benefits.</p>
5.28 Professional Bodies	Awareness raising within own community
5.29 Manufacturers	Awareness raising within own community
5.30 Other Stakeholders? Businesses?	Awareness raising within own community

6 Methods of Communication

What methods of communication will be used, how often and for what purposes? A non-exhaustive list of HIT2GAP communication activities are listed below:

6.1 Email/ EMDESK	Inter team communication – daily.
6.2 Website/ Flipboard/ Twitter/ Blog	<p><u>Website</u> – <u>Purpose</u> - wide scale dissemination. Regular (weekly) updating as required depending on stage of project, impending and recent deadlines. Link to EU added value on homepage. Reinforced by pointers in social media and press. <u>Aim</u> - Hits: 5000 (year 1), 7500 (year 2), 10,000 (year 3), 15,000 (year 4). Total: 37,500.</p> <p><u>Flipboard</u> – <u>Purpose</u> - quick sightings of things of interest – less formal.</p> <p><u>Twitter</u> – constant information feed.</p> <p><u>Blog</u> – link to newsletter and Flipboard.</p>
6.3 Social Media – Linked in / Facebook, etc.	<p><u>LinkedIn Groups</u> presence - <u>Purpose</u> – key contact with relevant professional groups - awareness and interest raising.</p> <p>Other mediums (such as Facebook and emerging sites) to be evaluated.</p> <p><u>Aim</u> - Group members: 300. “Likes” tracked.</p>
6.4 Traditional Media (TV, Radio, Press)	<p><u>Purpose</u> – to broadcast project key messages and events. 2 televised videos. 10 press releases. 5 radio spots.</p> <p><u>Aim</u> – to effect interest – monitored through Webpage “spikes” and email queries.</p>
6.5 Partner Marketing and Community Events	<p>HIT2GAP partner organisations already have far reaching marketing campaigns surrounding their products and linked to community events.</p> <p>Make use of Newsletter, Flyer and HIT2GAP Powerpoint presentation to promote project at such events.</p> <p><u>Purpose</u> – to reach a wide potential commercial and user base/ audience.</p> <p><u>Aim</u> - HIT2GAP displayed at 10 partner events and project visibility contributing to 1,000,000 views.</p>
6.6 Unique Partner Communication Channels	<p><u>Flyer</u> – <u>Purpose</u> - general outline information on project to be made available to all partners to use at events and for general publicity. Update only if info gets out of date.</p> <p><u>Newsletter</u> – <u>Purpose</u> – 6 monthly updates on project status, milestones reached and other issues. Otherwise use Web/ Flipchart.</p>

	<p><u>Aim</u> – Produce Newsletter every 6 months –</p> <p><u>Distribution List</u> see below - via stakeholders and other influencers identified by partners. (Minimum 25,000 readers).</p> <p>Communication:</p> <p>NBK - Newsletter diffusion (11000 contacts database, mainly French contacts)</p> <p>IK4-TEKNIKER (TEK) participates in international events and conferences related to EE such as Sustainable Places (http://sustainable-places.eu/) where we chaired two sessions. TEK is member of the IoTForum (http://iotforum.org/) that organizes the IoTWeek (http://iot-week.eu/) international event. This event is related to the application of IoT technology to various domains, including EE.</p> <p>FISE active member of the German Facility Management Association</p> <p>BRE twitter reaches 20,000 people in industry, government, etc. BRE news and building for change communication reaches 10,000 industry, government, etc. BRE publications are subscribed to by 5,000 users and can be bought as one-offs by any member of the public.</p> <p>MOS - Project presentation and leaflets distribution at the ECTP events (European Construction Technology Platform) www.ectp.org. WRS - Organization one national workshop with cooperation with City of Warsaw dedicated to construction and ESCO companies and building managers/owners.</p> <p>Goal - Contribution toward 1,000,000 views.</p>
6.7 Portraits and Testimonials	<p>Emotions surrounding the project's key messages captured and displayed across communication channels. Testimonials generated and shared.</p> <p><u>Purpose</u> – wider awareness raising and engagement with non-technical audience.</p> <p><u>Aim</u> - 5 Emotions Images and 20 Testimonials generated.</p>
6.8 Use of the stakeholder community and its network	<p>The HIT2GAP Stakeholder Community will contain actors inside and outside of the EEB sector.</p> <p>Make available Newsletter, Flyer and HIT2GAP Powerpoint presentation to promote project at such events.</p> <p><u>Purpose</u> – to interact and engage with the project and be positioned as both exploitation and communication agents from both inside and outside of the industry.</p> <p><u>Aim</u> - 200 members.</p> <p><i>We already received 25 Letters of Support (LOS). The stakeholders who signed the LOS already cover the whole</i></p>

	<p><i>set of HIT2GAP stakeholder, as a consortium we will leverage these first supporters to attain more and grow as planned during the project.</i></p>
<p>6.9 Dissemination events as communication activities: Conferences/ Workshops/ seminars/ trade fairs</p>	<p><u>Purpose</u> - To advertise the project to the research and development communities and to product innovators. Formal outputs at key points and depending on what we have to say at particular junctures. Frequency will depend on what is happening and when. Project team to be kept apprised by dissemination partners but also to take responsibility for making all partners aware of local and sectoral opportunities as they arise.</p> <p>EEB value chain specific conferences and trade fairs. Examples include ECTP events, the E2BA project database, Information Days at the EU, and sector Scientific Conferences that pair scientific and public dissemination. Also an opportunity for awareness raising – e.g. Sustainable Buildings Conference, EcoBuild.</p> <p>See Appendix 3 for guidance on HIT2GAP procedures for preparation of conference and journal papers.</p> <p>Make use of Newsletter, Flyer and HIT2GAP Powerpoint presentation to promote project at such events.</p> <p><u>Aim:</u> 40 events/conference participations</p>
<p>6.10 Publishing to EEB topic area platforms</p>	<p>We will leverage the website BuildUP – Energy Solutions for Better Building (www.buildup.eu) and others like it: ECTP - European Construction Technology Platform (www.ectp.org) PLEA – Sustainable architecture and Urban design, etc.</p> <p><u>Purpose</u> – To reach a wider audience beyond the project boundaries.</p> <p><u>Aim</u> - Views: 5000.</p>
<p>6.11 BRE and NBTK/INEF4 Networks / Stakeholder Meetings</p>	<p><u>Purpose</u> - Communication of key messages through these important partner communication and dissemination channels to a professional audience.</p> <p>Make use of Newsletter, Flyer and HIT2GAP Powerpoint presentation to promote project at such events.</p> <p><u>Aim</u> – 10,000 Views</p>
<p>6.12 Lectures, training, curriculum activities, etc.</p>	<p>LIU, UDG, GAL, UOS, EGE are exceptionally positioned to include HIT2GAP in lectures, training and curricula.</p> <p><u>Aim</u> - 20 inclusion occurrences.</p>

7 Communication Activities and Measuring Outcomes

Media / Events	Objective	Message	Frequency	Delivered to:	Delivered by:
7.1 Email	Cross and inter team communication	Various/ general	Continuous	Project team	All
7.2 Web, Newsletter, Flyer, etc.	Wide scale communication – professionals and wider public (make use of Newsletter, Flyer and HIT2GAP Powerpoint presentation to promote). – Aim – 37,500 hits (by year 4)	Constant information feed to wide audience	Continuous	General – public and lay audiences	BRE/ R2M/ ALL
7.3 Social Media	Key communication with relevant professional groups – Aim – 300 'likes'	Awareness and interest raising	Continuous	Professional and technical audiences	BRE/ R2M
7.4 Media	Broadcasting of key project messages and events (make use of Newsletter, Flyer and HIT2GAP Powerpoint presentation to promote).	To grow wider interest – monitored through Webpage 'spikes' / enquiries	2x TV videos 10 Press releases 5 Radio spots	General / lay audiences	TBA
7.5 Partner Events	To reach a wider potential commercial and user base/ audience (make use of Newsletter, Flyer and HIT2GAP Powerpoint presentation to promote). - Aim – 1,000,000 views	Awareness raising through trusted partners and events	Minimum - 10 events over 4 years	Commercial and user audiences	ALL

Media / Events	Objective	Message	Frequency	Delivered to:	Delivered by:
7.6 Unique/ Partner	To update professional and commercial audiences on progress (make use of Newsletter, Flyer and HIT2GAP Powerpoint to promote). - Aim – 25,000 readers by year 4 contributing to 1,000,000 views	Updates on project status, milestones reached and other issues. General project information to use at events and for general publicity.	Newsletter - 6 monthly Flyer – opportunistic	Partners and commercial/professional audiences	ALL especially: NBK/ TEK/ FISE/ BRE/ MOS
7.7 Testimonials	Project's key messages captured and displayed across communication channels. Testimonials generated and shared. – Aim – 5 emotions images and 20 testimonials	Wider awareness raising and engagement with non-technical audience.			
7.8 Stakeholder Forums	Use stakeholder forums and additionally stakeholders to disseminate and share project story across wider networks (provide them with access to / use of Newsletter, Flyer and HIT2GAP Powerpoint to promote). - Aim - 200 members to reach 200,000 audience by multiplier effect.	Keep industry insiders and outsiders informed of project progress	Via regular local stakeholder meetings	Stakeholders	ALL

Media / Events	Objective	Message	Frequency	Delivered to:	Delivered by:
7.9 Conferences and seminars	To advertise the project to the research and development communities and to product innovators. (make use of Newsletter, Flyer and HIT2GAP Powerpoint to promote). See Appendix 3 for guidance on HIT2GAP procedures for preparation of conference and journal papers. – Aim - 40 events/ participations	Up to date dissemination at key events to raise project profile as it evolves.	As opportunities arise – ALL to keep BRE informed of opportunities	Research and development communities	ALL
7.10 EEB platforms – BuildUP, ECTP, PLEA, etc.	To reach a wider audience beyond the project boundaries. - Aim – 5,000 views	Communication of project key messages and objectives	Continuous	Professionals and academics beyond the project boundaries	ALL
7.11 BRE/ NBK INEF4	Keep professionals apprised of progress - (make use of Newsletter, Flyer and HIT2GAP Powerpoint to promote). - Aim – 10,000 views	Communication of key messages through partner communication and dissemination channels to a professional audience.	As opportunities arise – ALL to keep BRE informed of opportunities	Professionals	ALL
7.12 Training/ education	Include HIT2GAP in lectures, training and curricula. - Aim – 20	Raise awareness of state of the art research and delivery in this area	Throughout project life and beyond	Students and Professional CPD	LIU, UDG, GAL, UOS, EGE

8 Summary and Conclusions

This document sets out the HIT2GAP Marketing and Communications strategy and the roles and responsibilities of all 22 Project Partners in delivering the project aims how success will be measured.

The marketing and communication strategy links back to the original project work plan which outlines the intentions with regard to communication, dissemination and exploitation and the role of project partners in delivering this. The overall aim is to align the project within a strategic innovation context and to make the project foreground scalable, replicable and high impact. It should be read in conjunction with Appendices 1: National Stakeholder Forum, 2: Initial Exploitation and Business Plan, and 3: Guidance for journal and conference paper submission and with reference to section 2 (Impact) of the original HIT2GAP project submission..

The engagement of national and overall project Stakeholder Forums is seen as crucial to the project's success. This will be constructed at a national level by individual partners with recommendations sought for participation at a project level. Throughout the duration of the project, this body is informed, engaged, and invited to participate in project events, project results, and progress with the objective of them becoming advocates of project exploitable results and in time the early and first adopters of the HIT2GAP approach, solution and services.

The Group will cover a broad spectrum within the 'dissemination space' and include the full range of stakeholders types / actors (building owners, energy managers, facility management companies, technology providers, building and sustainability consultants).

Beyond this the project team will work beyond our own consortium boundaries to include other sectors and other markets. Sector awareness, IPR positioning and deliberate technology and patent scouting will ensure that the project can position its foreground correctly and in a strong way. This is conducted by a dedicated exploitation partner (R2M) and leads into the management of exploitable results.

9 APPENDICES

9.1 APPENDIX 1: EU PROJECT HIT2GAP – NATIONAL STAKEHOLDER FORUM

Briefing document for project partners:

The project

The programme, involving 22 European research institutes, organisations and companies, will lead to improvements in the energy performance of commercial public buildings. It will seek to enable the development of an innovative platform that can be used with existing building management systems by building managers. The emphasis is on cost effective solutions that result in a reduction between the modelling and actual performance of buildings.

National Stakeholder Forums

National Stakeholder Forums (NSFs) will be formed in each country. These groups will be composed of representatives of national governments, local government, professional bodies, energy/environment agencies, industry (consultants, contractors, suppliers, manufacturers, energy modellers, etc) and local business forums. The intention of the NSF will be to provide support to the project from each country and to represent the interests of the country and its industry in the research. The NSFs will effectively have a role to help to steer and advise the project team.

NSFs are central to the dissemination of the project findings as well as providing a role in feedback via project partners.

Process

Groups of partners should work together in each country in order to create and run their NSF.

The following activities below should be addressed by partners:

- Identify a project partner in each country to organise the NSF activities over the project period (National NSF lead). Note that all partners shall be involved in the work of the NSF.
- Work with project partners in your country to identify potential members of the NSF in each country. A minimum of 10 members of the forum should be identified in each country, but in larger countries larger forums would be preferred.
- Write to stakeholders and invite them to participate (use summary and membership form to assist the process).
- National NSF lead to organise first meeting of the NSF for your country, invite members, include an agenda and project information.
- Date of first meeting to be between months 7 and 12 of the project.
- Subsequent meetings to be held at no greater than 6 month periods over the project.
- Partners to agree on a chair for each national stakeholder forum (may be a partner or a relevant stakeholder).

- National NSF lead to record and prepare minutes of the meeting(s); make minutes available to BRE/Nobatek within 28 days of the date of the meeting. Minutes to contain any main points of feedback related to the project, reports or the HIT2GAP approach. Also, send the minutes of meetings to NSF members.

Their role

The NSFs will become an important route for dissemination of the project and will create a network by which a successful research project will have its results implemented.

The NSF can do the following:

- Consider the big picture
- Link what the project is doing and planning to developments, problems and opportunities in the wider world.

The NSF should be made up of a mixture of backgrounds, partners should:

- Make clear to members what their likely responsibilities and time commitments will be (note there is no budget to pay time/expenses)
- Ensure clarity of both individual and group roles
- Produce minutes that include clear action lists showing who will take each action
- Create time for debate of the issues in the meeting
- Issue papers at least a week before meetings to allow the members sufficient preparation time
- Meet as regularly as is necessary to keep abreast of the progress of the project
- Try to maintain enthusiasm for the project at all times.

Further advice on the operation and management of the national NSFs can be obtained by contacting BRE directly.

Project background

Highly Innovative building control Tools Tackling the energy performance GAP

Technologies for improved performance of the built environment in relation to energy performance

Summary

The programme, involving 22 European research institutes, organisations and companies, will lead to improvements in the energy performance of commercial public buildings. It will seek to enable the development of an innovative platform that can be used with existing building management systems by building managers. The emphasis is on cost effective solutions that result in a reduction between the modelling and actual performance of buildings.

Aim

The 'performance gap' between the design and operation of a building's energy performance is well documented and verified by measurement campaigns. It is well documented that common errors across the four phases of construction can lead to a performance gap that can range between 150% and 250% of the original design specification. Systematically addressing these errors and thus reducing the gap between design and performance is the main objective of the HIT2GAP project.

Strategy and methodology

HIT2GAP will link enabling technologies and approaches used in the commissioning and operation phases of construction to improve the comparative predictions of the models and simulations that drive design, construction and the actual performance of new and retrofit buildings. To do this, the project will undertake the challenge of defining and enabling new solutions and products for building energy management which out-perform proprietary systems, with a view to identifying opportunities to improve existing approaches and enabling new innovations to come into the market. As such, HIT2GAP aims to link large system providers and small but highly innovative start-up companies by providing a platform that can integrate third-party systems and applications.

Impacts

This project will act as a springboard to the use of the next generation of innovative energy management technology.

HIT2GAP focuses on the commissioning and operation stages of the building life cycle to reduce the gap between expected and actual energy use, which according to the Green Construction Board count up to 35%. The project will do that by developing tools that can support complete and rigorous commissioning and also BMS and control audits to ensure once the building is running at its optimum it stays there.

To do so it is necessary to monitor, understand, model, predict control and support building operation. At this regard, different studies show some key impact findings for effective energy efficiency through two complementary factors, enhanced data analysis and occupant behaviour consideration.

HIT2GAP has the potential to save 20% to 25% savings; the potential is even higher in the future, as community activities can easily be designed around the core value discussed above.

The challenge is not the benefit itself, which according to all evidence will be paramount, but the time it will be required for this benefit to materialize. Correct data interpretation and behavioural change is underestimated and not well understood. To accomplish this, HIT2GAP will include enhanced data treatment modules for monitoring real time building operation and occupancy data and real-time meteorological and building performance data that will be used to continuously calibrate the models to more accurately represent the real energy behaviour.

Partners

The project is being coordinated by NOBATEK in France; the full list of partners is as follows:

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Participant short name	Country	Org. type
1	NOBATEK	NBK	France	RTO
2	EURECAT	EUR	Spain	RTO
3	IK4-Tekniker	TEK	Spain	RTO
4	Fraunhofer ISE	FISE	Germany	RTO
5	Building Research Establishment	BRE	UK	RTO
6	Bouygues Energies & Services	BES	France	IND
7	Giroa	GIR	Spain	IND
8	Mostostal	MOS	Poland	IND
9	CYLON Controls	CYL	Ireland	IND
10	R2M	R2M	Italy	SME
11	Abo Data	ABO	Italy	SME
12	Apintech	API	Greece	SME
13	CyRIC	CYR	Cyprus	SME
14	Zutec	ZUT	Ireland	SME
15	Enerit	ENR	Ireland	SME
16	Evolution	EVL	France	SME
17	City of Warsaw	WRS	Poland	GOV
18	Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour (LIUPPA)	LIU	France	UNI
19	University of Girona	UDG	Spain	UNI
20	University of Galway	GAL	Ireland	UNI
21	University of Strathclyde	UOS	UK	UNI
22	Ege University	EGE	Turkey	UNI

Timetable

1st September 2015 to 31st August 2019.

National stakeholder forums

National stakeholder forums (NSFs) will be formed in each country. These groups will be composed of representatives of national governments, local government, professional bodies, energy/environment agencies, industry (consultants, contractors, suppliers, manufacturers, energy modellers, etc) and local business forums. The intention of the NSF will be to provide support to the project from each country and to represent the interests of the country and its industry in the research. The NSFs will effectively have a role to help to steer and advise the project team.

In return the NSF members will have access to the research results at an early stage, in advance of the publication of the findings. In addition, members will have access at reduced rates to dissemination events that will be organised by the partners. The NSFs represents a substantial opportunity to network with key stakeholders in the field of energy management through regular meetings of the group and virtual networking through a project web site.

To join the [enter country] NSF please complete the attached form and return to [enter partner].

Further information can be obtained from the [enter country] based research partners, contact details as follows:

<i>ADD DETAILS IN TABLE</i>	

Horizon2020 Programme

Highly Innovative building control Tools Tackling the energy performance GAP

National Stakeholder Forum – Membership Form

Please complete this box as fully as possible

Organisation	
Contact name	
Address for correspondence	
Telephone	
E-mail	
Nature of Business	
State if public or private sector	

Please return this form to [enter partner details]:

By post to:

E-mail:

9.2 APPENDIX 2: Initial Exploitation and Business Plan

HIT2GAP assembles a full value chain of end users, technology providers, consultants, and industrially active RTOs to both conduct the research and also to carry the project foreground to the market post project. Due to the diversity of the consortium partner stakeholder types, sectors of expertise and business geographic areas, the primary means of exploitation and business planning in HIT2GAP will be the integration of the HIT2GAP foreground into each partner’s current areas of business with the expectation that synergies and referrals will present themselves over the course of the collaboration. By partner, and written by each partner, initial partner exploitation plans are as follows.

Consortium Value Chain and Partner Exploitable Planning:

Stakeholder Type	Initial Exploitation Plan
Universities (knowledge, education, training and academic dissemination)	<p>LIU - use the project pilots to validate innovative research approaches and methods in some real scenarios and cases; cope with new challenges (Big Data, self-adaptive programming and interactive environments).</p> <p>UDG - knowledge transfer opportunities on data driven methods for energy modelling and assessment with BMS companies and end users.</p> <p>GAL – partnership with ZUTEC and support to other Irish companies in the field of building operation; national research projects on the back end of HIT2GAP with local stakeholders.</p> <p>UOS - integrate the open source background technologies and methods (for building simulation, pervasive sensor deployment and services delivery) with the developments undertaken by the other project partners as a means to achieve a new solution that has good potential for widespread uptake.</p> <p>EGE – act as the Gateway for exchange of personnel and ideas between EU and Turkey both at the academic level and at the company level (BMS and construction companies).</p> <p>ALL - publication to key journals and conferences, future research projects, expose large student body to the ideas and methods emerging from the project as a means to support future innovation within the construction sector .</p>

<p>Research Organisations (close to market development, technology transfer and consulting focus)</p> <p>Technical solutions development and support</p>	<p>NBK – license platform data treatment modules with a TRL >7; demonstration of the ability to reach important >30% savings with advanced data treatment approach.</p> <p>TEK - bring technological knowledge to the surrounding industrial ecosystem. Turn HIT2GAP into competitive offers for potential local industrial clients. Building on top of the TIBUCON project technologies as well as increase TEK expertise in the application of IoT related technologies to the EE domain.</p> <p>FISE - further development of the FDD-Framework to consolidate its offer for services in the field of building monitoring. Enlarge the industrial clients portfolio with a special focus on BAS/BMS manufacturers who are interested in integrating FDD algorithms in their systems.</p> <p>BRE – Develop new consultancy opportunities, development of training modules for industry/building owners on how to close the gap. Potential certification of new technology or advanced performing buildings (e.g. BREEAM or product certification).</p>
<p>Technology providers</p>	<p>CYL – integrate a new level of intelligence into current BMS product offerings for commercial buildings, gain in competitiveness and generate new market opportunities.</p> <p>ABO - enter the market related to energy saving and efficiency with a greater spectrum of product offerings and innovative M2M interfaces.</p> <p>API – increase the value and possibilities of its Wireless things (WT) solution. Develop and commercialise the activity MODULE that can model of user behaviour, describing how users operate the building, brings forward a technology to meter space occupancy.</p> <p>ZUT – develop and sell new solutions that integrate building simulation and BIM to the current facility management actions tool.</p> <p>ENR – further enhance and develop its own products in line with the questions being asked by ISO 50001 certified companies around how the demonstrate and implement continuous improvement. Focus on integration of energy management system into everyday business planning and management systems in line with achieving higher levels of Energy Management Maturity.</p> <p>ALL – become more competitive and cross sell technologies in each other’s markets.</p>

<p>End users (building owners, management companies, consulting suppliers) (building facility ESCOs, service)</p>	<p>BES - choose and optimize the prediction algorithms and integrate them in Hypervision®. Data collected with Hypervision® will be used to evaluate and tune the various algorithms; this will be used to increase FM performance with current clients and attain more clients (e.g., more buildings to manage).</p> <p>GIR - market the new HIT2GAP ICT-based solution along with their products and services, which are suitable for almost all the markets where Gira-Veolia is involved offering energy efficiency: tertiary, and to a lesser extent, health and industry sector.</p> <p>MOS – become a more competitive construction company through the development of additional services (HIT2GAP) that can be included in the tender offer.</p> <p>R2M – gain more clients in Italy that seek for building operation support and reach out to current LEED certified estates in order to commercialise the innovative HIT2GAP services.</p> <p>WRS – become more energy efficient by adopting the HIT2GAP solution across different public buildings. Integrate the old buildings and drive the design of new ones according to HIT2GAP best practice. Support the Development Strategy for the City of Warsaw until 2020 with innovative solutions.</p>
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9.3 APPENDIX 3: Guidelines for preparation of conference/ journal paper

As HIT2GAP is a multi-partner project, it is necessary to have a structure around which associated papers are prepared:

1. Any intention to develop a conference or journal paper should be highlighted to all partners via EMDESK in order to avoid conflict of interest; clashes in timing (e.g. with milestone delivery, IPR issues, and other issues relating to timing, etc.); duplication potential and to maximise the exploitation opportunities;
2. Within the timescale of the project, it is not acceptable to exploit the project unilaterally – this could result in missed opportunity and thus co-operation is vital;
3. Agreement regarding which partners should contribute and how this will be managed should be agreed with Nobatek as project managers;
4. Lead authors names should headline with other contributors listed in alphabetical order;
5. Prior to submission, the preparation of an Abstract, will provide an opportunity to make all partners aware of the intention from the outset and to enhance the project;
6. Any focus on the project that goes beyond what is in the public domain should be cleared with project partners via EMDESK and coordinated through Nobatek;
7. The potential to use the National and Project Stakeholder Forums in preparation of papers is legitimate but again must be cleared by all partners via Nobatek to avoid any risk of conflict of interest;
8. Papers should be prepared according to conference/ journal guidelines, fully referenced and logged as pertaining to the HIT2GAP project with full credit given to all participating partners;
9. Time should be managed to allow all partners should be given adequate opportunity to comment on final paper prior to submission; and
10. Partners should be apprised of outcomes and given the opportunity to attend the presentation if appropriate.